

A STUDY OF NICKEL REINFORCED WITH TUNGSTEN WIRES,

A POTENTIAL HIGH TEMPERATURE MATERIAL

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Fabrication by liquid infiltration has been investigated. It is possible to produce specimens of 3 mm diameter and 10-15 cm length with continuous tungsten fibres in a nickel matrix; the fibre diameter is 0.5 mm and the volume percent is up to 50. The quality of the composites is acceptable. The mechanical properties in tension have been found to agree with the law of mixtures; the strength is unusually low at temperatures below 300-400°C, but acceptable at temperatures up to about 1000°C. The creep strength at 800 and 900°C is in reasonable agreement with expected values based on composites with creeping fibres.

Introduction

This report describes work carried out to study the fabrication and mechanical properties of a potential composite for high temperature applications. The composite has a nickel matrix with continuous fibres of tungsten; this system is considered a model for nickel alloys reinforced with strong and stiff fibres, which are possible candidates for applications in e.g. gas turbines. The work is carried out on laboratory scale, but the results are probably indicative of performance in practice and can form the basis for intelligent guesses. The work has been sponsored by the Scandinavian Research Council (Nordforsk).

Fabrication

The composites are made by casting (liquid infiltration) of nickel around a bundle of long tungsten wires. The fabrication method used in the laboratory is illustrated in fig. 1, which is a sketch of the apparatus. The mould of aluminium-oxide is heated by an HF-induction coil via a molybdenum adaptor. The assembly is protected by an argon atmosphere in a silica tube. The loading of the mould, heating, casting and cooling will take 2-3 hrs, which is considered relatively fast. This method is particularly suited to produce cylindrical specimens with long parallel fibres. The composites have the following characteristics:

- maximum density (no porosity)
- no mechanical damage to the fibres
- thermal treatment of the fibres, due to temperatures from c. 1100^o to c. 1400^oC, and the pres-

- ence of liquid nickel, cause some recrystallization in the surface layer of the tungsten fibres, and some reaction between nickel and tungsten.
- the fabrication temperature is higher than the expected service temperature
 - volume per cent of fibres can be up to 50%
 - fibre diameter is 100-500 μ
 - specimen diameter is 3-5 mm
 - specimen length can be up to 15 cm
 - the matrix has large grains (\sim 1 mm).

The problem of initiation of recrystallization in the tungsten fibres is not solved, but the composites show low strengths (brittle behaviour) only at temperatures below about 400 $^{\circ}$ C, which is believed to be the ductile-brittle transition temperature of tungsten. The reaction between matrix and fibres causes a layer of 5-10 μ to be dissolved. These two effects may cause some reduction in mechanical properties, but as the service temperature (about 1000 $^{\circ}$ C) is lower than the fabrication temperature, and as the aim has been to study the mechanical properties in relation to models for composites, we have not considered these effects important for the present study. For long time service it is of greatest importance to establish barrier layers or other means of controlling the thermal stability.

The raw materials for the composites are nickel of purity 99.998% (supplied by Johnson, Matthey & Co.) and commercially doped tungsten wires (supplied by Mullard).

In the following sections comparison is made with composites fabricated by a sinterforging method (Kannappan 1974) where the fabrication temperature is about 1100 $^{\circ}$ C. These composites are made from nickel powder and tungsten fibres of diameter 300 μ .

Tensile Properties

Tensile testing at room temperature of composites with long fibres shows scattered and low ultimate tensile strengths for the cast composites, and better values for the sinterforged composites. This is believed to be due to partly recrystallized, brittle fibres in the cast composites. A linear relationship between strength and volume fraction is established for both types of materials, in agreement with simple composite models for (brittle) fibres in a ductile matrix (Kelly, Davies 1965, Mileiko 1969). This relationship is used to extrapolate to the fracture strength of the fibres; this strength is very difficult to measure directly on the (brittle) fibres.

The critical volume fraction is 10-20%, and therefore composites with volume fractions below this range show multiple fracture of the fibres. Although the multiple fracture process may not have been complete, an estimate of the critical length l_c is made from histograms of the distribution of fibre segment lengths. From the relationship

$$\frac{l_c}{d} = \frac{\sigma_{fu}}{2\tau}$$

and by using the estimated values of σ_{fu} we can calculate τ , the shear strength at the interface. The value of τ is about 25 kp/mm² for special, slowly cast composites and 10-12 kp/mm² for the ordinary, cast composites and the sinterforged composites. The high value in the former case is probably an approximate value of the shear strength in the reaction zone, and the lower value in latter case is probably indicative of little, if any, reaction at the interface.

Tensile testing in vacuum at temperatures from room temperature to 1100°C is made on both types of composites. The data for the strength of composites are used to estimate the fracture strength of the fibres and then to derive, from the rule of mixtures, the ultimate tensile strength at nominal volume fractions of 15%, 25% and 40%. These derived data are compared in fig. 2. Above about 400°C the two types of composites are nearly identical, with slightly higher values for the cast composites. Below about 400°C the brittle fibres in the cast composites cause the measured strength to be very low and scattered.

Creep Properties

Cast composites with 25% and 45% of long tungsten fibres of diameter 500 μ have been creep tested in air at 800°C and 900°C. The minimum creep rate has been plotted versus the stress in fig. 3a and fig. 3b. The theory for continuous composites is based on the law of mixtures for the stresses on the two components creeping at the same rate (Street 1971). Based on literature data for pure nickel (Shahinian, Achter 1959) and for pure tungsten (Harris, Ellison 1966) the expected lines for various volume fractions have been drawn in the figures. The experimental data show the expected slopes, but the absolute magnitude of the predicted stresses is overestimated. It is probable that the discrepancy is caused by inaccurate literature data for the calculations, in particular for the fibres. It can be noted that at 800 and 900°C the 25% composite has a creep strength of about ten times the strength of the pure matrix.

A comparison is made in fig. 4 with literature data

on other nickel alloy-tungsten systems; a direct evaluation is difficult because of the various materials and conditions used. It is believed that the cast composites show a creep behaviour comparable to other similar composites.

Applications

The mechanical properties for the model composite of nickel-tungsten are probably indicative of the performance of more practical composites based on nickel-alloys and fibres with the necessary barrier layers. In this context tungsten has a very high density which may be detrimental to the performance of the composite, e.g. in rotating components in gas turbines. It is, however, important to consider the effect of density on the strength of the composite itself, fig. 5. In this schematic diagram the shape of the curves is governed by the relative density of matrix and fibres. The heavy fibres impose a relatively rapid increase in the strength/density ratio in the region of low volume fractions. As practical conditions (fabrication, corrosion-protection) may require composites of only low to medium volume fraction, e.g. 20-50%, the high density of tungsten fibres may not be so critical. This point has also been discussed by Glenny (1970).

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APPARATUS FOR CASTING (VACUUM INFILTRATION)

Fig. 1: Sketch of the apparatus used for casting nickel-tungsten composites by vacuum infiltration.

COMPARISON OF σ_{UTS} (DERIVED VALUES)

Fig. 2: Ultimate tensile strength of cast composites and of sinterforged composites as a function of testing temperature in vacuum. The data are recalculated at nominal volume fractions of 15%, 25% and 40%.

Fig. 3: Minimum creep rate of cast composites as a function of stress; predicted lines for the creep behaviour are drawn.
 (a) 800°C; (b) 900°C

Fig. 4: Minimum creep rate as a function of stress, for several nickel alloy-tungsten systems and at various testing temperatures.

Fig. 5: Strength/density ratio of composites as a function of volume fraction; the curves are calculated for approximate values of the ultimate tensile strength of the components at 1100°C.